

Full paper

Characterisation of the Long Bolts in Tension

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Abstract

The RFCS CONNECT4C European Research Project aims to enhance the adaptability and reusability of steel structures through the development of innovative joint configurations, in which long bolts play a critical role in load transfer mechanisms. Despite their growing use, long bolts lack thorough research and standardised design rules. This study presents an extensive experimental and analytical investigation into the tensile behaviour of long bolts to characterise their performance and validate existing design methodologies. A total of 66 tensile tests were conducted, examining the influence of key parameters, including four bolt diameters (M20, M24, M27, and M30), two bolt grades (8.8 and 10.9), surface finishes (black and galvanised), and configurations with single or double nuts. Experimental results are compared with the tensile resistance and stiffness predictions given in EN 1993-1-8, demonstrating that current design equations are applicable to long bolts. A material model for long bolts is proposed with constant values for strain hardening and ultimate strains according to the bolt grade. Finally, a reliability analysis conducted in accordance with Annex D of EN 1990 confirms the adequacy and safety of the existing formulations for use in design under tensile loading.

Keywords

Long bolts, Tensile resistance, Stiffness, EN1993-1-8, Experimental investigation

1 Introduction

In this study, long bolts are defined as structural fasteners fabricated from circular steel rods, rather than coiled steel, and exclude heat-treated variants. Unlike standard structural bolts, which face length limitations, long bolts are employed where conventional bolt heads are impractical or extended grip lengths are necessary.

The European RFCS CONNECT4C Project [1] underscores the importance of such bolts in developing demountable joints with high tolerance for reclaimed steel members [2]. These joints predominantly subject long bolts to tensile forces. However, despite their growing use, long bolts remain understudied in the literature and lack explicit coverage in product standards.

This paper addresses this gap by investigating the tensile behaviour of long bolts and assessing the applicability of EN 1993-1-8 [3] design rules, formulated for standard bolts, to long bolts. An experimental campaign evaluates

their tensile response, followed by a critical examination of EN 1993-1-8's tension resistance and stiffness provisions. A reliability analysis, aligned with EN 1990 Annex D [4], validates the proposed partial factor (γ_{M2}) to ensure compliance with target safety thresholds.

2 Literature review**2.1 Previous investigation**

Long bolts play a crucial role in modern structural systems, particularly in applications requiring connections between non-adjacent components. Their increasing adoption in demountable construction solutions promotes adaptability and material reuse, aligning with sustainable building practices. Notably, their high deformability makes them ideal for innovative self-centring systems [5-6], while their extended length facilitates connections in challenging configurations, such as concrete-filled steel tubes [7].

Fransplass et al. [8] studied long bolts under combined

tension and shear loads at low and elevated strain rates. For performing the tests, authors used a purpose-made fixture and tests specimens with the maximum grip length of 9.8 mm. They pointed out the influence of thread number within the grip length on the failure mode and ductility.

Unlike long bolts, conventional bolts have been studied widely. Recent work by Stranghner et al. [8] revisited the design resistance of carbon steel bolts subjected to tension, shear, and combined loading. Through an extensive experimental campaign and reassessment of prior test data, the authors demonstrated that the current design provisions in EN 1993-1-8 [3] could be optimised while still satisfying the target reliability criteria established in EN 1990 Annex D [4].

Grismo et al. [10] showed that by increasing the nut height, the probability of thread stripping failure decreases, and the probability of bolt fracture increases. They also considered the use of high nuts according to ISO 4033: Hexagon high nut [11] to avoid thread stripping failure.

Additionally, the threading configuration significantly influences bolt performance under tensile loading. Yang et al. [12] conducted a numerical investigation comparing the fracture behaviour of partially threaded (PT) and fully threaded (FT) bolts. Their results demonstrate that while PT bolts exhibit approximately 15-20% higher yield and ultimate tensile strength, this comes at the expense of reduced deformation capacity compared to FT counterparts.

2.2 Long bolt definition

Figure 1 depicts the geometric configuration of a long bolt assembly with single nuts. The investigated bolt consists of a fully threaded rod, although partially threaded variants are also commercially available. Key dimensional parameters are total bolt length (L), bolt elongation length (L_b), grip length (L_g), thread engagement length (L_{tl}), and nominal bolt diameter (d).

Figure 1 Long bolt geometry definition [13].

EN 1993-1-8 [3] gives an expression for the tensile resistance of fully and partially threaded standard bolts as:

$$F_{t,Rd} = \frac{k_2 f_{ub} A_s}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (1)$$

where k_2 is a reduction factor (with $k_2 = 0.9$, except for countersunk bolts $k_2 = 0.63$), f_{ub} is the nominal tensile strength of the bolt, A_s is the tensile stress area of the bolt, and γ_{M2} is the partial safety factor ($\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$).

The standard [3] provides specifications for the tensile stiffness of a bolt row. For preloaded bolts, the initial

stiffness is theoretically assumed to be infinite (rigid behaviour). For a non-preloaded individual bolt, the initial tensile stiffness is calculated as:

$$k_b = \frac{0.8EA_s}{L_b} \quad (2)$$

where E is the Young's Modulus of the bolt material, and L_b is the bolt elongation length.

3 Definition of the experimental programme

In the present study, long bolts were tested under isolated tensile loading, with the main goal of obtaining force-displacement ($F-u$) curves. A total of 66 tensile tests were conducted. The following parameters were considered:

- Bolt diameter: M20, M24, M27 and M30;
- Bolt grade: 8.8 and 10.9;
- Surface finishing: B – black and G – galvanised;
- Number of nuts: N1 – single and N2 – double nut.

Long bolts with the smaller bolt diameters (M20 and M24) were provided in both bolt grades (8.8 and 10.9), while the long bolts with bigger bolt diameters (M27 and M30) were tested only in 10.9-grade because of economic reasons. All tests were repeated 3 times to increase the variability of the results.

All tested bolts had a constant total length (L) of 1000 mm. The grip length (L_g) varied depending on the nut configuration (single or double nut assembly) and the combined thickness of washers and nuts. In all configurations, the bolt end protruded approximately 5 threads beyond the nut face. Table 1 summarises the experimental grip lengths for both configurations ($L_{g,N1}$ - single nut assembly, and $L_{g,N2}$ - double nut assembly), along with the corresponding nominal tensile resistances calculated using Equation (1).

Table 1 Operational grip lengths and nominal resistance of the bolts [13].

No. of nuts / Grade		M20	M24	M27	M30
N1	$L_{g,N1}$ mm	935	922	916	907
N2	$L_{g,N2}$ mm	903	882	872	859
8.8	$F_{t,Rd}$ kN	141.1	203.3	264.4	323.1
10.9	$F_{t,Rd}$ kN	176.4	254.2	330.5	403.9

The experimental setup (see Figure 2) consisted of: (1) a fixed bottom retaining beam to prevent vertical displacement; (2) a top retaining beam connected to the hydraulic jack (10) to transfer load to the specimen; (3) bolt-to-beam connection tools with 36 mm holes to accommodate all specimens; (4) a guiding system allowing beam movement along the reaction frame (6); (5) adjustment washers for standard bolt tolerances (22 mm, 26 mm, 30 mm and 33 mm for bolts M20, M24, M27 and M30, respectively); (7) supporting brackets to stabilize the bottom beam; (8) load cells for force measurement; and (9) a hinge linking the hydraulic jack to the upper beam. The reaction frame (6) provided structural support for the entire assembly.

Figure 2 Experimental layout: (a) 3D view; (b) Elevation with marked parts; (c) Photo from the test [13].

The experimental program employed displacement-controlled loading at a rate of 0.025 mm/s, applied vertically through a 6 MN capacity hydraulic jack (10) to the top retaining beam (2).

During testing, the following data were recorded:

- Applied force and reactions, measured with two load cells (8).
- Displacements, measured using LVDTs (Linear Variable Displacement Transducers).

Twelve LVDTs were strategically positioned to monitor both global system behaviour and local bolt response.

4 Test results

4.1 General

The experimental program comprised standardised tensile testing of long bolts following ISO 898-1 [14], with results systematically categorised by bolt grade (8.8 and 10.9) and nominal diameter. This primary dataset was augmented by the tensile tests on machined cylindrical coupons extracted from representative bolt specimens,

performed following ISO 898-1, and a comprehensive geometrical characterisation of a sample of specimens.

4.2 Geometrical characterisation

Table 2 Geometrical characterisation of the long bolts. [13]

Bolt	Class	Measurement	A_s (mm ²)	
			Black	Galvanized
M20	8.8	Mean	229.52	233.82
		Mean/Nominal	93.76%	95.52%
	10.9	Mean	240.47	243.54
		Mean/Nominal	98.23%	99.49%
M24	8.8	Mean	344.84	347.75
		Mean/Nominal	97.82%	98.65%
	10.9	Mean	342.34	346.48
		Mean/Nominal	97.12%	98.29%
M27	10.9	Mean	441.27	446.93
		Mean/Nom	96.05%	97.28%
M30	10.9	Mean	549.82	554.44
		Mean/Nom	98.08%	98.90%
		Max CoV	0.91%	0.97%
All	/	Max CoV	0.91%	0.97%

Geometrical characterisation of the long bolt specimens

was performed using a calliper (0.01 mm resolution) to measure critical dimensions, including external diameter, internal diameter, and pitch length. Measurements were conducted across representative samples grouped by bolt diameter, material class, and surface finish. The tensile stress area (A_s) for each configuration was calculated according to ISO 898-1 [14] provisions and is presented in Table 2 [13]. The resulting values demonstrate exceptional dimensional consistency, with all specimens exhibiting a coefficient of variation (CoV) below 1 % for the calculated tensile stress areas.

4.3 Material characterisation

The mechanical properties of the bolt materials were determined through standardised coupon testing in accordance with ISO 898-1 Clause 9.7 [14] and ISO 6892-1 [15], producing complete stress-strain curves for analysis. Key material parameters, presented in Table 3, are the stress at 0.2% non-proportional elongation ($R_{p,0.2}$), the tensile strength (R_m), the stress at the rupture point (R_r), the total percentage elongation corresponding to the tensile strength (A_{gt}), and the percentage elongation at fracture (A).

All tested specimens met the minimum requirements specified in ISO 898-1 of $R_{p,0.2,min} \geq 660$ MPa, $R_m \geq 830$ MPa, $A \geq 12$ %, for class 8.8 and $R_{p,0.2,min} \geq 940$ MPa, $R_m \geq 1040$ MPa, $A \geq 9$ %, for class 10.9.

Table 3 Material characterisation of the long bolts. [13]

Class		$R_{p,0.2} = f_y$ (MPa)	$R_m = f_{ub}$ (MPa)	R_r (MPa)	A_{gt} (%)	A (%)
8.8	Mean	880.3	983.6	669.8	8.58	17.0
	Mean /Nom	1.38	1.23	-	-	1.42
	CoV	4.3%	3.5%	5.3%	5.6%	5.0%
10.9	Mean	1101.0	1177.9	800.8	6.48	13.9
	Mean /Nom	1.22	1.18	-	-	1.55
	CoV	2.3%	1.8%	5.1%	10%	7.1%

4.4 Force-displacement curves

The force-displacement response, presented in Figure 3, reveals distinct behavioural patterns between single-nut (N1, see Figure 3a) and double-nut (N2, see Figure 3b) configurations. Graphical representation differentiates failure modes through markers (circles for bolt fracture (BF), stars for thread stripping (TS)) and surface treatments with line styles (solid for black bolts, dashed for galvanised).

All double-nut assemblies failed exclusively through BF, while single-nut configurations predominantly exhibited TS failures (see Figure 4). The BF failures demonstrated superior performance characteristics, including enhanced ductility and more consistent maximum load capacities. Notably, half of the 10.9-grade bolts that failed by TS did not reach their nominal yield stress.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3 Force-displacement curves: (a) Single nut tests (N1); (b) Double nut tests (N2) [13].

Figure 4 Failure modes: (a) Thread stripping; (b) Bolt fracture. [13].

Bolt grade significantly influenced the response, with 8.8-grade bolts exhibiting greater ductility than their 10.9-grade counterparts. Also, only M20 8.8 bolts displayed a distinct yield plateau.

The experimental initial stiffness values showed excellent agreement with Equation (2) predictions, yielding a mean ratio of 0.98 with a coefficient of variation (CoV) of 7.93%.

5 Long bolt material model

In recent years, advanced finite element software has become an essential tool for sophisticated structural analysis in the research community. The accuracy of such numerical simulations critically depends on the application of properly validated material properties for all model components. To address this need, a specialised material model for long bolts was developed. In [13], the procedure is explained in detail, and is only summarised here. The model parameters were derived through comprehensive material characterisation, including standardised coupon tests conducted following ISO 898-1 [14].

The proposed model is based on Yun and Gardner's [16] model for the hot-rolled steel material:

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} E\varepsilon & \text{for } \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_y \\ f_y & \text{for } \varepsilon_y < \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_{sh} \\ f_y + (f_u - f_y) \left[0.4\varepsilon^* + \frac{2\varepsilon^*}{(1 + 400\varepsilon^{*5})^{0.2}} \right] & \text{for } \varepsilon_{sh} < \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_u \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\varepsilon^* = \frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh}}{\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

The primary difficulty when applying Equation (3) lies in determining two critical strain parameters: the strain hardening strain (ε_{sh}) and the ultimate strain (ε_u). While these are conventionally expressed as functions of the yield-to-tensile strength ratio (f_y/f_u), experimental data from coupon tests [13] revealed substantial scatter in these values (for instance, a 36.5% CoV for ε_{sh} in 8.8-grade bolts). Notably, the f_y/f_u ratio showed limited correlation with the observed strain limits.

To address this variability, constant values for ε_{sh} and ε_u are proposed based on the bolt grade:

$$\varepsilon_{sh} = \begin{cases} 0.015 & \text{for class 8.8 bolts} \\ 0.0089 & \text{for class 10.9 bolts} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_u = \begin{cases} 0.086 & \text{for class 8.8 bolts} \\ 0.065 & \text{for class 10.9 bolts} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The proposed material model, incorporating these constant strain values, demonstrated excellent agreement with experimental coupon test data. Quantitative evaluation revealed an average coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.996 when comparing modelled and measured full stress-strain curves across all tested specimens.

6 Reliability assessment

6.1 Methodology

The statistical evaluation follows the reliability framework prescribed in EN 1990 Annex D [4], adopting a target reliability index of $\beta = 3.04$ corresponding to the reliability class RC2. As defined by Equation (1), the probabilistic assessment of steel bolt tensile resistance depends on two key parameters: (1) material tensile strength (f_{ub}) and (2) tensile stress area (A_s). Material characterisation results indicate coefficients of variation (CoVs) of 3.5% and 1.8% for tensile strength in 8.8 and 10.9 class bolts, respectively.

For consistency with current research benchmarks [9], this study adopts 4% CoV for tensile strength and 1% CoV for tensile stress area.

6.2 Statistical evaluation of γ_{M2} safety factor

The reliability analysis yields a safety factor of $\gamma_{M2}^* = 0.955$ when using the standard $k_2 = 0.9$ factor specified in EN 1993-1-8, increasing to $\gamma_{M2}^* = 1.061$ for $k_2 = 1.0$ as proposed by Stranghoner et al. [9]. These values, derived for both 8.8 and 10.9 long bolts, consistently exceed those reported by Stranghoner et al. for conventional structural bolts ($\gamma_{M2}^* = 0.88$ with $k_2 = 0.9$ and $\gamma_{M2}^* = 0.98$ with $k_2 = 1.0$), highlighting the distinct reliability characteristics of long bolts compared to standard variants.

7 Conclusions

This study presents an extensive experimental investigation of long bolts under tensile loading, evaluating critical parameters including bolt diameter, material grade (8.8 and 10.9), nut configuration (N1/N2), and surface treatment through 66 systematic tests. The observed failure modes correspond to the findings for conventional structural bolts, with double-nut assemblies consistently failing through bolt fracture (BF), while single-nut configurations frequently exhibited thread stripping (TS). Analytical verification confirmed the applicability of EN 1993-1-8 provisions for both tensile resistance and initial stiffness estimation in long bolt applications. Material behaviour analysis revealed greater ductility in grade 8.8 bolts compared to grade 10.9 specimens. Additionally, a material model for the long bolts, incorporating grade-specific constant values for strain hardening (ε_{sh}) and ultimate strain (ε_u), is proposed.

The reliability assessment suggests that adopting an increased k_2 factor of 1.0 (as proposed in recent literature) may improve tensile resistance predictions while maintaining the target reliability index ($\beta = 3.04$). However, this finding warrants further examination regarding potential reliability differentiation between bolt grades and configurations.

Acknowledgements

This work was partly financed by:

- The European Commission's Research Fund for Coal and Steel through the research project CON-NECT4C (High-strength steel connections for circular construction), ref. no. 101112300, is highly

acknowledged. Disclaimer: "Work is funded by Europe Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

- FCT / MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB / 04029/2020 (<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04029/2020>), and the Associate Laboratory Advanced Production and Intelligent Systems (ARISE) under reference LA/P/0112/2020.

References

- [1] Silva, L.S.; Ljubinković, F.; Conde, J.; Alves, T.; Demonceau, J.F.; Neutellers, A.; Odenbreit, C.; Bogdan, T.; Mela, K.; Bernabeu, A.; González, G. (2023) *CONNECT4C: High-strength steel connections for circular construction*. RFCS-02-2022-RPJ, Deliverable D1.1 – Comprehensive overview of the project.
- [2] Janković, N.; Dobrić, J.; Gluhović, N.; Conde, J.; Ljubinković, F.; da Silva, L.S. (2024) *Numerical characterization of innovative demountable beam-column connections using long bolts*. *ce/papers*. 7(1–2), pp. 45–54.
- [3] European Committee for Standardization (2005) EN 1993-1-8:2005: *Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-8: Design of joints*. Brussels, Belgium.
- [4] European Committee for Standardization (2002) EN 1990:2002: *Eurocode – Basis of structural design*. Brussels, Belgium.
- [5] Elettore, E.; Freddi, F.; Latour, M.; Rizzano, G. (2022) *Parametric study and finite element analysis of self-centring steel column bases with different structural properties*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 199, 107628.
- [6] Lettieri, A.; de la Peña, A.; Freddi, F.; Latour, M. (2023) *Damage-free self-centring links for eccentrically braced frames: development and numerical study*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 201, 107727.
- [7] Van-Long, H.; Jean-Pierre, J.; Jean-François, D. (2015) *Extended end-plate to concrete-filled rectangular column joint using long bolts*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 113, pp. 156–168.
- [8] Fransplass, H.; Langseth, M.; Hopperstad, O.S. (2011) *Tensile behaviour of threaded steel fasteners at elevated rates of strain*. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*. 53(11), pp. 946–957.
- [9] Stranghöner, N.; Abraham, C.; Ehrhardt, L. (2024) *New design approaches for tension, shear and interaction resistance of carbon steel bolts*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 212, 108260.
- [10] Grimsmo, E.L.; Aalberg, A.; Langseth, M.; Clausen, A.H. (2016) *Failure modes of bolt and nut assemblies under tensile loading*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 126, pp. 15–25.
- [11] European Committee for Standardization (2012) ISO 4033:2012: *Hexagon high nuts*. Brussels, Belgium.
- [12] Yang, F.; Veljkovic, M.; Liu, Y. (2021) *Fracture simulation of partially threaded bolts under tensile loading*. *Engineering Structures*. 226, 111373.
- [13] Janković, N.; Ljubinković, F.; Conde, J.; Costa, J.; Silva, L. (2025) *Behaviour and design resistance of long bolts in tension*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 229.
- [14] European Committee for Standardization (2013) ISO 898-1:2013: *Mechanical properties of fasteners made of carbon steel and alloy steel – Part 1: Bolts, screws and studs with specified property classes – Coarse thread and fine pitch thread*. Brussels, Belgium.
- [15] European Committee for Standardization (2019) ISO 6892-1:2019: *Metallic materials – Tensile testing – Part 1: Method of test at room temperature*.
- [16] Yun, X.; Gardner, L. (2017) *Stress-strain curves for hot-rolled steels*. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 133, pp. 36–46.